

ISic3341

I.Sicily inscription 3341

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

volcanic

Object

tabula

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Provenance unknown, seen by Libertini (1921) 'nel giardino Acunto sito nel vicolo Sinagra'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334863

1. [— — —]NICIP [— — — — — —]
2. [— — —]io Hirtian [o — —(?)— —]
3. [— — —]QVI[—(?)—]LVPO [—(?)—]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645586

PHI 334863

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 755

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 229 no.8 dr

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3341. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388424>